

Lesson study in the context of open schooling for teacher education

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Abstract. This paper outlines an exploratory research work investigating the potential of Lesson Study for teacher professional development within the context of sustainability education in open schooling. Open schooling, a comprehensive learning approach, integrates formal, non-formal, and informal education, engaging students in addressing real-life sustainability challenges in collaboration with universities and communities. Despite its promise, open schooling remains relatively underrepresented in the literature, especially in relation to Lesson Study, STEM education, and the incorporation of real-life socioscientific issues. This paper reviews existing literature on these topics and provides recommendations for teacher educators seeking to enhance sustainability education within open schooling through innovative methodologies.

Keywords: Lesson Study, Open Schooling, Teacher Education, Real-life Socioscientific Issues.

1. Introduction

The concept of open schooling is often used more broadly and can encompass a variety of educational approaches and practices that promote openness, flexibility, and innovation in education. This term has been promoted by the European Union since 2015. Open schooling involves transforming schools into centers of well-being where students collaborate with their families, communities, and expert professionals to address real-life problems that contribute to sustainable development. This approach aims to nurture students' scientific thinking skills, fostering their problem-solving abilities and, in turn, cultivating a heightened interest in pursuing careers in the field of science [1]. In the CONNECT project, which focuses on inclusive open schooling with a forward-looking perspective on science education, open schooling is firmly grounded in engagement and enjoyable learning principles. It emphasizes education as a socially transformative and inclusive process that highly regards diversity and meaningful learning [2].

This article posits Lesson Study as a viable approach for supporting teacher education within the open schooling context. This action research teaching strategy was designed to foster classroom-based, engaging activities **to solve** real problems perceived by students, thus creating an enriching and enjoyable learning environment. Lesson Study, often abbreviated as LS, is presented as an alternative method to facilitate collaborative teacher professional development. Its core purpose is to enhance the quality of education and address learning challenges [3]. The LS concept revolves around a teacher

professional development model rooted in collaborative learning, emphasizing principles of mutual learning to continually enhance teaching practices [4], [5].

In this study, our primary objective is to investigate **the potential of LS** in raising awareness of sustainable development within the framework of open schooling. Our specific research questions (RQ) encompass the following:

- (RQ1) In what ways Lesson Study could be implemented for teacher education in the context of open schooling?
- (RQ2) In what ways existing literature regarding Lesson Study in science education could be used to inform teachers' educators interested in open schooling?
- (RQ3) What are the similarities between Lesson Study and the coaching model SEEK used in the CONNECT open schooling project?

2. Methodology

Our methodology centred on: • A scoping review conducted using academic databases such as Scholar and Emerald Insight. • Inclusion criteria: Articles published in English in scientific journals within the past five years. • Exclusion criteria: Book chapters, reviews, handbooks, and studies that did not investigate LS and its application to scientific issues.

In the assessment process, a total of 41 articles were reviewed to determine their relevance to the study's objectives. Out of these, only three articles were found to meet the inclusion criteria, demonstrating the selectivity of the research process.

These three articles focused on various issues related to science education and pedagogy. The primary themes analysed within these selected articles included scientific literacy and communication skills, scientific argumentation, and science thinking skills. This deliberate focus on key aspects of science education allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the effectiveness of LS in enhancing these critical skills.

The nature of the studies in the selected articles varied, demonstrating a diverse approach to investigating the impact of LS on science education. The research designs included descriptive-qualitative methods, a mixed-method approach, and purely qualitative methods. This methodological diversity enriched the depth of insights and perspectives available for the study, providing a well-rounded understanding of the subject matter.

Additionally, these studies were conducted in different countries, showcasing a global perspective on the implementation of LS in science education. The countries where the research took place were China, Norway, and Indonesia. The geographical diversity of the studies further emphasized the universality and adaptability of LS as an approach to improving science education. This cross-cultural dimension added valuable insights into the effectiveness of LS in diverse educational contexts, enriching the study's findings.

3. Findings

(RQ1) In what ways lesson study could be implemented for teacher education in the context of open schooling?

According to [6], educators engaged in LS in Japan and the United States demonstrated that participating professionals benefited from successful LS practice in seven ways: deepening their knowledge of the subject studied, gaining a better understanding of instruction, improving their ability to observe students, forming stronger professional networks, establishing a stronger connection between daily practice and long-term goals, increasing motivation and a sense of efficacy, and enhancing the quality of lesson planning.

LS is conducted iteratively and can occur in a cyclical manner through four phases [7]. Traditionally, LS is implemented with groups of teachers who together go through four collaborative steps: i) curriculum study and goal formulation; ii) planning, which involves the selection and detailed review

of the research lesson; iii) teaching, where one team member teaches the research lesson while others observe and collect data; and iv) reflection on their own practice and beliefs to enhance it [3], [8], [9], as demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Source: The Lesson Study Group at Mills College [10].

(RQ2) In what ways existing literature regarding Lesson Study in science education could be used to inform teachers' educators interested in open schooling?

In investigating the effectiveness of contextual learning for scientific attitude and student performance in Natural Sciences, [11] suggest the adoption of the LS approach to counter conventional teaching, where teachers, possibly due to a lack of knowledge about alternative teaching methods, continue to provide rigid and ready-made instruction. According to these authors, LS is suitable for promoting cooperation among teachers to observe their own practices and collaboratively develop strategies to foster an active stance in students. The goal is for student-centered learning to increase their interest and promote healthy and positive social interaction to achieve learning objectives while enhancing critical thinking skills for contextual scientific issues among students.

In a similar vein, in the Netherlands, the Freudenthal Institute has partnered with a team of high school science teachers to promote sustainability education following the LS approach. In this initiative, science teachers and researchers explore the opportunities of socioscientific inquiry-based learning to facilitate the planning of lessons on environmental citizenship and address the challenge of preparing students to form responsible opinions on such topics [12]. This issue concerns the knowledge about and of science that citizens need to critically consider scientific findings and analyze the complexity of socioscientific issues in order to make informed decisions in their daily lives, taking into account different values [13].

In a recent international systematic review study, [14] analyzed the implementation of socioscientific issues as teaching and learning materials in science education and how different stages are developed in the learning process. The findings indicated that primary studies implementing LS achieved successful results both in terms of teacher professional development and student learning improvement. The study emphasizes that the difference lies in the fact that while most implementations of socioscientific issues

are focused solely on student learning, initiatives that adopt the LS approach promote a sustainable cycle of actions aimed primarily at teacher professional development, which is rare in this area. Therefore, the successful integration of science learning in the educational context is inseparable from the teacher's or facilitator's ability to apply it. These initiatives have shown that investing in developing teaching skills to work collaboratively on socioscientific issues, from planning to teaching, observation, and analysis of learning and teaching, directly reflects in better student learning outcomes.

It is observed that the implementation of socioscientific issues in educational contexts varies in different countries and cultures or traditions. Therefore, problems related to socioscientific issues that arise in one country may simply not exist in others [15]. Thus, socioscientific issues differ from other scientific issues because they are open, unstructured, and contextual problems [16]. They are open because they lack a direct answer or solution, and unstructured due to their controversial nature, as well as potentially having scientific explanations and connections to various other areas of knowledge [15].

(RQ3) What are the similarities between Lesson Study and the coaching model SEEK used in the CONNECT open schooling project?

Given the open-ended nature of LS and Coaching scenarios, it is crucial for teachers to engage in collaborative discussions about their individual requirements, challenges, interests, and effective strategies. These discussions serve to foster the exploration and implementation of scientific topics tailored to local needs. The success or obstacles in implementing and discussing socioscientific issues in teaching and learning processes depend on teachers' perceptions of their feasibility. The LS approach provides an opportunity for teachers to reflect on their long-standing practices and begin to form new beliefs related to creating a meaningful learning atmosphere in an open schooling context. However, studies on how the implementation of socioscientific issues in the open schooling context can be supported by the LS approach are limited.

According to [17], efficient teacher training is crucial for overcoming pedagogical difficulties already experienced by teachers and for the appropriation of new pedagogical strategies in an unfamiliar open schooling context. To facilitate the development and monitoring of the LS approach, the coaching model called SEEK (acronym for Start, Establish, Explore, Key) suggested by [18] for personalized teacher training in the open schooling context can be used during the complexity process experienced by teachers. The LS approach and SEEK have congruent and complementary characteristics suitable for the open schooling context.

The SEEK model also consists of four stages: i) the start, which aims to build trust for the process, where goals and expectations will be aligned; ii) the exploration and establishment stage of a new perspective allows participants to recognize where they are and what needs to be done to achieve established goals; iii) the stage of exploring options and action planning aims to understand potential pathways that will allow the achievement of goals and identify feasible deadlines for the completion of proposed tasks; iv) the recognition of major achievements is the final stage of the process, where participants have the opportunity to reflect on the progress made and, by identifying key results, each member should be encouraged to acknowledge their effort and achievements [18]), as shown in Fig. 2.

Both LS and the SEEK coaching model share a cyclical and iterative approach, organized into distinct stages. LS traditionally comprises four collaborative phases: curriculum study and goal formulation, planning, teaching, and reflection. Similarly, the SEEK coaching model also consists of four stages: start, exploration and establishment, exploring options and action planning, and recognition of major achievements. In both models, the iterative nature allows for continuous improvement, and the structured phases facilitate the collaborative development and reflection of teaching practices, ultimately enhancing the professional growth of educators.

Figure 2. Source: **CONNECT SEEK coaching model (2022)**.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this article has explored the potential implementation of LS within the context of open schooling, with a particular focus on enhancing science education. The research has highlighted how LS, a well-established action research teaching method, can offer valuable insights and benefits to teachers and students involved in open schooling initiatives.

LS, conducted iteratively and often in a cyclical manner through four distinct phases, has been demonstrated to bring about several positive outcomes. These include deepening teachers' subject knowledge, improving their understanding of instruction, enhancing their ability to observe students effectively, fostering stronger professional networks, strengthening the connection between daily teaching practices and long-term goals, increasing motivation and self-efficacy, and elevating the quality of lesson planning.

Furthermore, the study has delved into the existing literature regarding LS in the context of science education and how this body of knowledge can inform teacher educators interested in open schooling. This review has showcased successful applications of LS, particularly in promoting science education, by encouraging cooperation among teachers and enhancing critical thinking skills, student engagement, and problem-solving abilities. The research also highlighted the need for teacher professional development to ensure successful implementation. Additionally, the article has drawn attention to the similarities between LS and the SEEK coaching model, as both models share a cyclical and iterative approach structured into distinct stages. This similarity underscores their compatibility and the potential for their collaborative use in open schooling contexts.

Overall, the findings suggest that LS, with its well-documented benefits, has the potential to be a valuable tool for promoting open schooling, enhancing science education, and providing teachers with the means to collaboratively address real-world issues while fostering student engagement and problem-solving skills. Furthermore, the congruence between LS and the SEEK coaching model offers a promising avenue for supporting teacher development in open schooling initiatives, ultimately contributing to the success and sustainability of this educational approach.

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